

Fostering Improved Training Tools For Responsible Research and Innovation FIT4RRI

Content map & supporting structures (Deliverable 4.1)

Deliverable Responsible: UMinho

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the first output within Task 4 - Training tools and actions - of the FIT4RRI project. The Task is focused on the adoption of Responsible Research and Innovation/Open Science (RRI/OS) good practices in research funding and performing organizations (RFPOs). The purpose of this FIT4RRI output - a Content mapping and meta-analysis of RRI/OS training - is to support the training activities carried out by the consortium partners, as well as the testing, in different RFPOs, of procedures triggering the kind of institutional change that favors new governance settings and new training approaches.

This deliverable specifies the rationale applied in the content mapping, together with a classificatory scheme and a training-related taxonomy that seeks to encompass key dimensions of both RRI and OS that are themselves driven by expected learning outcomes. The proposed taxonomy and classificatory scheme rest heavily on the combined experience of FOSTER and RRI Tools networks, accumulated during a four-year long period of reflexive practice within a wide European alliance of RRI/OS actors and stakeholders.

In addition, the deliverable puts forward an initial core of resources/content for RRI/OS training, compiled and mapped in compliance with the proposed taxonomy and classificatory scheme. Given the fast growing body of RRI/OS knowledge, practices and tools, this is a dynamic content mapping that is designed to be fed and nurtured by the unfolding of the FIT4RRI tasks and actions. This preliminary content is presented alongside a meta-analysis of the resources, which are themselves largely based of the most effective and far reaching resources compiled by both the FOSTER and RRI Tools projects.

1. Content mapping and meta-analysis of RRI/OS training

Combining both RRI and OS in a single taxonomy of training resources is an unprecedented challenge, and one that is not entirely risk free. Despite their obvious differences, not least of a conceptual nature, there are enough commonalities, both procedural and practical, that justify, in our eyes, the undertaking of such a challenge. The authors and contributors to this exercise emerge from two apparently distinct frameworks. On the one hand, the RRI Tools project has built an alliance of RRI hubs scattered across 30 European countries to provide a comprehensive toolkit for the training and dissemination of responsible research and innovation (RRI). On the other, the FOSTER project has gathered partners from all over Europe to ensure that open science (OS) becomes the norm, particularly by producing an e-learning platform that brings together the best training resources addressed to those who need to know more about open science to foster its practices in their daily workflows.

Coming from such diverse networks, and driven by their distinctive goals, it was possible, through a collective debate of mindsets and frameworks, to build a common ground, whilst accounting for the specificities that underpin and identify RRI and OS. We are, nevertheless, fully aware of the fact that the construction of an effective RRI/OS taxonomy can be no other than a work in progress, and one that is likely to be reinforced, as much as disproved, by the training practices that it is built to serve.

1.1 A roadmap to an integrated taxonomy

The first step in the co-creation of a comprehensive RRI/OS taxonomy involved a meta-analysis of the training resources that are part of both the RRI Toolkit (rri-tools.eu) and the FOSTER's e-learning platform (fosteropenscience.eu). In so doing, we tried to avoid having, on the one hand, taxonomy terms for which there would be no relevant resources to be classified with, and, on the other, to have topics lacking the granularity required to address an extensive and diverse body of resources.

Figure 1 - Distribution of the resources on the FOSTER Portal according with the OS Taxonomy

The proposed taxonomy builds on the taxonomy developed by the FOSTER project (www.fosteropenscience.eu), and used to categorize the resources on the FOSTER Portal (<https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/resources>). During the lifetime of the project, FOSTER collected more than 2000 training resources on the Portal, most of them produced and resulting from the 100 face to face training events supported or organized by FOSTER. The main categories of the FOSTER Open Science Taxonomy, which collect the vast majority of the resources (see Figure 1).

On the other hand, following a path of integration, the present proposed taxonomy drew also on a meta-analysis of the training resources that are part the RRI Toolkit.

Figure 2 - Distribution of the resources on the RRI Toolkit Portal

The meta-analysis of the RRI Toolkit accounts for a number of key dimensions that are, unsurprisingly, coincidental with those proposed by the European Commission as policy agendas for the implementation of RRI. And these are public engagement, open access, gender, ethics, science education and governance.

Public engagement is one of the most populated term in the RRI Toolkit, with up to 54% entries in its database. Being essentially a multi actor, multi stakeholder, collaborative process, that is designed to align the outcomes of research and innovation to the values, needs and expectations of society, RRI requires an effective public engagement in all the stages of the process, from the setting of the research agenda to the public communication of its results. If there is a visible trait characterizing the RRI training resources, it is indeed that of public participation. In many ways, it mirrors the paradigm shift that has been marking the evolution of the public understanding of science over the past decades; that is, the shift from popularization of science to participation in science. Citizen science, participatory research and innovation are, therefore, prevalent strands in the RRI training resources for public engagement, in tune with a growing attention to science and society interconnections, co-production of knowledge and dialogue-oriented forms of communication.

Science education and scientific literacy are yet another facet of the above concern for public engagement. Accounting for 35% of the RRI toolkit training and advocacy resources, it shows the extent to which public participation in research and innovation debates requires a citizenship that is equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills. The purpose of training resources for science education, from an RRI stance, is not circumscribed to school science. Indeed, it appears to be more in line with the current practices of informal science learning environments, such as museums, science

centers or other formal-informal partnerships and collaborations. From an RRI perspective, science education is also about providing opportunities to understand the nature of scientific challenges, their application to real-world problems and ultimately, their societal implications, through first hand contact with the processes of science and the cultural environment in which they take place.

Open access to scientific publications and results is key for an informed public engagement, for the quality of science learning, for a more responsive dialogue with society and, finally, for a more productive research and innovation. As it were, it stands right at the intersection between RRI and OS. In that sense, from an RRI perspective, the concept of open access (OA) is increasingly embracing the free access to the scientific data (OD) that underpins publications or research. Therefore, 46% of the RRI Toolkit database addresses both open access and open data, whereas in the FOSTER e-learning platform, OA and OD, combined, account for 67% of its training resources.

Gender, as an RRI policy agenda, encompasses action in three distinct dimensions. The first seeks to reduce gender segregation in research and innovation, ensuring a balanced representation of women, particularly in domains where these are (under) represented, such as STEM. The second attempts to remove organizational barriers to women participation in top management positions and decision-making processes. The third, finally, concerns issues of gender in research and innovation content, as well as in the subjects of research, language and discourse. All together, these dimensions are covered by 25% of the resources included in the RRI Toolkit.

Governance of RRI/OS, that is “steering innovation through the establishment of goals, the establishment of means and the verification of performance” requires robust arrangements. These include being able to plan and implement organizational change, identify and evaluate policy levers available to help it, facilitating and building partnerships and networks, and funding instruments to support RRI/OS. Such an encompassing agenda is extensively reflected on the RRI Toolkit, and “governance” describes 57% of the resources on the platform.

Ethics, of course, is at the core of the ideal of responsible research and innovation. Ethics refers to the integrity of research and innovation, that is, how both the outcomes and the processes of R&I should be morally grounded and acceptable to society; RRI fundamentally aims at integrating ethics across the entire R&I process, from policy making and agenda setting to funding call formulation, project definition and proposal writing, to project execution and evaluation. This ambitious goal requires continuous orientation, reflection and deliberation. About 35% of the contents of the RRI Toolkit are covered by the descriptor “ethics”.

1.2 A focus on learning outcomes

The present deliverable is an output of Task 4.1, a task included in the “analytical strand” of FIT4RRI, which aims at developing a comprehensive analysis of RRI and OS in European RFPOs. According to the FIT4RRI DoA, tasks belonging to this strand should take into account RRI/OS general trends, barriers, drivers, interests and values, and advanced experiences. Tasks in WP4 Training tools and actions should therefore attend to 1) what is happening in the development of RRI/OS competences and skills; 2) the factors limiting the increase in RRI/OS competencies and skills; 3) the factors promoting the increase in RRI/OS competencies and skills; 4) the interests and values involved with the development of RRI/OS competences and skills; and 5) successful experiences in development of RRI/OS competences and skills.

Task 4.1 stated goals was to **evaluate the landscape of existing training materials and review the materials** in light of the analytical dimensions presented above. More specifically, T4.1 sets in

motion a content mapping, applying a taxonomy of training resources in OS/RRI, which provides the backbones for a continuous collection of quality training content throughout WP4.

In line with these principles, the evaluation, classification, taxonomy design and mapping of extant RRI/OS resources was explicitly driven by training purposes, hence the focus on the learning outcomes, that are assigned to each of the main topics in the taxonomy. The proposed learning outcomes are grounded on the experience of two previous FP7 projects, FOSTER and RRI Tools, themselves strongly focused on identification of materials for training and delivery of training for OS and RRI respectively.

The learning outcomes presented on section 3 were informed by:

- the FOSTER Open Science Learning Objectives¹, which outlines simplified Open Science LO for the main stakeholders in the Research Ecosystem, structured by Open Science topics according to the OS Taxonomy and in levels of competence.
- the RRI TOOLS Learning Outcomes² were grounded in an iterative process, throughout a series of workshops across Europe with more than 400 quadruple helix participants, arranged in 5 stakeholder groups: policymakers; business/industry representatives; civil society organisations; researchers and innovators; and the education community (both formal and informal).

Figure 3 - RRI Learning Outcomes Analytic Dimensions

The workshops offered insights on how quadruple helix actors across Europe understand RRI, and allowed for the mapping of needs, constraints and inspiring practices they identified for training on RRI, the usage of a RRI Toolkit and advocacy of RRI. Issues, ideas, suggestions and examples

¹ Grigorov, I., Carvalho, J., Ball, D., Bjørnshauge, L., Cancellieri, M., Davidson, J., Swan, A. (2015, February 23). FOSTER Open Science Learning Objectives. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15603>

² Smallman, M., Miller, S. (2016, April 6) D4.1 RRI Toolkit Training Programme, https://www.rri-tools.eu/documents/10184/107098/RRITools_D4.1-TrainingProgramme.pdf/15de5740-3ced-4011-9b3d-bc48ab4bc89a

produced in these workshops were translated into learning outcomes to be addressed in the training phase of the project.

An analysis of these RRI learning outcomes is presented here, as a concept map (Figure 3), with its main analytical dimensions.

Far from being normative, the proposed learning outcomes, encompassing both FOSTER and RRI Tools sources, will be enriched and iteratively adapted in the framework of the Proactive Strand, which includes elearning support, RRI training improvement, online training materials and exchanging of experiences between trainers and learners.

2. An integrated RRI/OS Taxonomy

Figure 4 - RRI/OS taxonomy map

3. RRI/OS Content Map and Learning Outcomes

MAIN TOPIC	SECONDARY TOPIC	LEARNING OUTCOMES
SCIENCE EDUCATION	Scientific literacy	<p>Recognize the role of education to raise awareness of the next generation of researchers and innovators about values, principles and procedures of research that is open being and sensitive to the needs of society. This includes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Being able to identify areas of curriculum relevant for RRI & OS that may need to be modified in order to present science in more reflexive ways, and acknowledging values, principles and procedures of research that is open and sensitive to the needs of society; 2. Being able to develop teaching and curriculum material presenting science in more reflexive ways, and acknowledging values, principles and procedures of research that is open and sensitive to the needs of society.
	RRI/OS in learning environments	
	Curriculum change	
REPRODUCIBLE RESEARCH	Irreproducibility studies	<p>Be able to define the relevance to reproducibility and justify openness as a reproducibility tool. This includes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifying OS tools for each step of the Research Lifecycle; 2. Defining the relevance of OS tools to reproducibility and integrity of research; 3. Applying OS concepts to daily research processes; 4. Discussing role of OS in the peer-review process <p>Discussing role of OS & reproducibility in innovation & economic growth.</p>
	Definition of Reproducible Research	
	Open Lab notebooks	
	Open Science Workflows	
	Open Source in Open Science	
	Reproducibility guidelines	
	Reproducibility testing	
OPEN SCIENCE EVALUATION	Open Metrics and Impact	<p>Identify and understand metrics and impact in the context of Open Science, recognizing altmetrics and other measures for scientific impact:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifying the suit of altmetrics for future research evaluation; 2. Stating the pros and cons of various altmetrics measures; 3. Interpreting and discussing OS contribution to Research Evaluation Assessments; 4. Understanding the use of academic networks scores; 5. Assessing standardized Usage Statistics for Open Access Repositories and Publication Services.
	Semantometrics	
	Bibliometrics	
	Webometrics	
	Altmetrics	
OPEN DATA	Open Big Data	<p>Understanding open research data, open big data, open data journals, open data standards, and open data use and reuse, by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Defining the concepts of open data; 2. Identifying services based on open big data; 3. Demonstrating the advantages of open data and the research data management links; 4. Identifying existing open data journals; 5. Preparing a publication for an open data journal;
	Open Data Journals	
	Open Data Standards	
	Open Data use and reuse	

	Open Data governance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Identifying existing open data standards; 7. Using identifiers for archiving and citing research data; 8. Understanding linked open data; 9. Selecting and using licenses (e.g. CC) for datasets Complying with Horizon2020 Open Research Data policy and other funder requirements.
OPEN ACCESS	Open Access Routes	<p>Be able to distinguish options for Open Access, recognize its advantages and reuse existing OA resources, by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Comparing cost/benefits of Gold and Green routes; 2. Choosing relevant route based on your context; 3. Complying with Horizon2020 Open Access Mandate; 4. Analyzing the social impact of OA; 5. Estimating the effect of OA on visibility and impact of research results; 6. Identifying tools and e-infrastructure for OA 7. Defining the characteristics of an OA publication 8. Using different OA search portals; 9. Interpreting content licenses and copyright,
	Open Access Use and Reuse	
GOVERNANCE	Funders policies	<p>Be able to identify and evaluate organizational mandates that are available to help implement RRI and OS. This includes being able to plan and implement organizational change, with the aim of fostering RRI and OS, and delivering research and innovation that are responsible and responsive to societal needs.</p>
	Governmental policies	
	Institutional policies	
	Organizational change	
RRI DEFINITION	<p>RRI Processes</p> <p>RRI Outcomes</p> <p>RRI Indicators</p>	<p>Understand what RRI is, where it has come from, and why it can introduce an important and beneficial shift in relations between research, innovation and citizens. This includes to understand:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The agendas covered by RRI; 2. The outcomes RRI is expected to deliver; 3. The processes that can aid the achieving of these outcomes; 4. How to find and work with partners to help to deliver RRI, and appreciate the standpoint(s) they may hold on RRI; 5. The opportunities that RRI can provide, particularly the new perspectives that working with other stakeholders may provide; 6. The obstacles that may stand in the way of delivering RRI, and the actions that may be required to overcome them; 7. What RRI, as whole, means; 8. How existing documentation and tools can help in understanding and implementing RRI; 9. The performance indicators for promoting and monitoring RRI.
RESEARCH WORKFLOW	RRI/OS proposal writing	<p>Be able to apply RRI and OS principles, processes and values in all stages of research, from research agenda setting to the communication of results. This includes:</p>
	Task definition	
	Problem specification	

	Analysis/experimentation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Being able to prioritize RRI and OS in research and innovation proposals; 2. Being able to anticipate contradictions between business interests and open and societally; responsible innovation and delivery, and be able to plan to address these issues.
	Data collection	
	Evaluation	
	Methodology	
RRI/OS POLICIES	Open Access policies	<p>Identifying OS and RRI policies, drafting OS and RRI policies, complying with Horizon2020 and monitoring its compliance, by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifying the different types of OS and RRI policies; 2. Formulating an OS and RRI policy to your discipline/project; 3. Identifying the requirements of Horizon2020 Open Access Mandate; 4. Complying with Horizon2020 Open Access Mandate; 5. Complying with Horizon2020 Open Research Data Pilot; 6. Defining metrics and tools to monitor compliance 7. Reporting level of compliance.
	Open Data policies	
	RRI policies	
	Advocacy for RRI/OS	
OS DEFINITION	Open data definition	<p>Being able to define the concept of Open Science. This includes, as learning objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Defining relevance of OS tools to Reproducibility/Integrity of Research; 2. Applying OS concepts to your daily research processes; 3. Discussing OS & Reproducibility role in Innovation & Economic Growth.
	Open Access definition	
GENDER	Gender equality policies	<p>Recognize the importance of inclusiveness and diversity for research and innovation and be able to implement plans to ensure the diversity, inclusiveness and gender balance of teams, institutions and workplace.</p>
	Gender sensitive research	
	Gender bias	
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT	Public understanding of science	<p>Be able to identify, foster and implement formats of public participation in all the phases of the research and innovation cycle. This includes being able to identify and implement formats of public participation in the setting of agendas for research and innovation, and put forward new research projects or ideas for products or services.</p>
	Participatory research and innovation	
	Citizen Science	
	Participatory research agenda setting	
ETHICS	Research integrity	<p>Be able to identify, discuss and apply ethical dimensions of research and innovation at individual, organizational and societal levels.</p>
	Intellectual property	
	Data protection and privacy	
	Human subjects protection	
	Animal care	

4. Content resources

In order to accomplish the objectives of Task 4.1 Content mapping and meta-analysis of RRI/OS training, it was decided to collect and categorize a representative sample (at least 100 resources) of training materials, especially the ones produced by related projects as FOSTER and RRITools.

For that purpose, an online form/spreadsheet was created to register, describe and categorize the training resources, following the FIT4RRI classification scheme presented in 4.1:

The use of this elements/field was established also as a way to facilitate the future upload of the identified resources into the FOSTER (Task 4.2).

FIT4RRI CONTENT RESOURCES COLLECTION

Resulting from this exercise, at the moment of concluding this deliverable, 120³ resources were selected, collected and described. The collected resources may be accessed here:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1uMAcz_MEN0H3cUDj8iXuq5yQMpJjaw7WMdQ4_yhGWEk/edit?usp=sharing.

The collection of resources will be expanded and updated in the following months, and throughout the entire duration of the project.

Analyzing the current collection of 120 resources, we found there is a generally balanced distribution across the main topics (RRI and Open Science) addressed by FIT4RRI, with around 1/3 (38) of the resources focusing on RRI, almost half (55) of the resources focusing on Open Science, and around 20% (26) of the resources covering topics across both RRI and Open Science.

Analyzing the collected resources by the target audiences they address, the first conclusion is that the vast majority of the training materials are addressed to more than one of the main stakeholder's groups (research, industry, education) and to several subgroups within each group (e.g., researchers, research administrators, project officers, etc.). Not surprisingly, the stakeholder group with higher representation on the collected resources in our sample is "Research" with more than 50 resources addressing that group. But each of the other main stakeholder groups identified – Civil Society Organizations, Education, Industry and Business, and Policymakers – are also served by a significant number of resources, varying around 40 to 50 training materials.

The vast majority of the resources are recent, with more than 60% (76) of the resources produced in the last 3 years (2015-2017), and only 10% (12) with more than 5 years (dates equal or before 2012).

Almost all (116) of the selected resources are in English language, with just a few resources in French and Portuguese. However, we are aware that there is a bigger number of relevant training resources (namely in the FOSTER Portal) on languages other than English (French, German, Polish, Portuguese, Spanish, and others).

Considering the categorization of resources according with the "Level of Knowledge" we've found that 65% (78) of resources are "Introductory", 27% (32) "Intermediate", and only 8% (9) were "Advanced" level.

Finally, regarding licensing of the resources we've found that around 65% (78) of the resources have no licensing information associated. This percentage is higher on the resources focusing on RRI, than on the materials about Open Science. Almost all resources with license information (40 on 41) use Creative Commons licenses, with CC-BY being the most common license (25 resources with that license).

³ Updated list: 04/09/2017

4.1 FIT4RRI Training Resources Classification

For the purpose of this task we define “training resource” as any resource that can help both training and learning about RRI and OS, as well as how to implement these in research and innovation processes. Considering this pragmatic definition, “training resources” include a wide range of formats and more specific aims, to be addressed in the *Description* field:

- Library materials, i.e., documentation that helps understanding what RRI and OS means, and raise awareness of this concept and its implications;
- Practices, i.e., inspiring examples that illustrate dimensions of RRI or OS at work in different real life settings;
- Tools that help think how to be more responsible and open in R&I: training tools for teaching staff, including materials to be used in the classroom; tools for implementing RRI and OS; tools for evaluating the performance of current practices on different aspects of R&I in terms of responsibility and openness; tools to disseminate and advocate RRI and OS agendas, etc.;
- Projects that explicitly address, investigate, put in practice, monitor and/or evaluate RRI and OS principles, values and processes.

#	FIELD NAME	FIELD DESCRIPTION	MANDATORY
1	TITLE	Name of the resource	yes
2	DESCRIPTION	Resource description, summary of content, summary of the purpose, type of tool, context to be applied, main features, summary of project aims, resources, activities, results	yes
3	AUTHORS/CREATORS	Author(s) and or institution(s) who developed the resource	yes
4	DATE	Date of creation or last update of the resource	yes
5	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	Scope level of the resource: Introductory (aware of) / Intermediate (able to) / Advanced	no
6	LANGUAGE	Language of the resource	yes
7	MAIN TOPIC	Main coverage of the resource based on the topics listed in the Taxonomy Table (all that apply)	yes
8	SECONDARY TOPICS	Secondary topics and Keywords/tags that can be used to describe the resource (all that apply)	no
9	LICENSE	Any specific licenses associated with the resource	no
10	AUDIENCE	Stakeholder(s) involved or potentially interested in the resource (all that apply): Research (RES) / Citizens (CSO) / Industry (IND) / Policymakers (POL)	yes
11	LINK	The URL where the resource can be found	yes